

The Employee Performance: Religious, Personality, and Physical Work Environment as Anticidents Study on Forest Holders Unity (Kph) Employees In Probolinggo City

Sudarsih
Departement of
Management, Economi
and Bussiness Faculty,
Jember University,

Supriyadi
Politehnik Negeri
Jember,

Susanti
Prasetyaningtiyas
Departement of
Management,
Economi and
Bussiness Faculty,
Jember University

Alwan Abdurahman
Politehnik Negeri
Jember
E-mail:

Ponti Primastuti Aulia
Nugraheni
Politehnik Negeri
Jember,

Abstract:- This research aims to analyze the influence of religiosity, personality and physical work environment on the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. The number of samples determined in this research was 72 respondents using a saturated sampling technique. The results of this research show that there is a partial significant influence (t test) of religiosity, personality and physical work environment on employee performance. The research results show that religiosity has a positive effect on employee performance. Religiosity has a positive effect on employee performance. Personality has a positive effect on employee performance. The physical work environment influences employee performance.

Keywords:- Employee Performance, Personality, Physical Work Environment, Religiosity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Management of a company with good performance of course has supporting components in achieving the company's goals. Apart from capital and technology, one of the supporting components that a company has is human resources (HR). This component will manage the company's operations both in terms of capital and technology. This management of course requires good competency so human resources need to be upgraded starting from skills to their perspective in looking at work. In this case, leaders are expected to be able to be aware of various factors that support the optimization of employee performance.

Regarding optimizing employee performance, Brahmasari and Suprayetno (in Alfisyah and Anwar, 2018: 100) argue that there are driving factors involved. One of them is supporting the psychological atmosphere of employees. This psychological atmosphere will influence the level of productivity of an employee. Employees who have problems in their work motivation will result in a decrease in productivity and performance. Supporting an employee's

psychological atmosphere can be done through encouraging employee religiosity.

Every existing religion certainly teaches various good things to each of its followers. Developing attitudes of religiosity in every activity carried out, including at work, will of course direct an employee to positive activities in accordance with religious teachings and rules. When you try to carry out the teachings and rules of the religion you adhere to, it will foster an attitude of wanting to give your best at work so that the resulting performance will be good too. This is of course in line with research conducted by Setiawan, et al (2001) and Aprilia, et al (2021) which states that religiosity influences employee performance.

Meanwhile, according to Mathis & Jackson (2012), one of the psychological drivers that can influence performance is personality. Personality is a characteristic that exists within an individual which can be seen from how they interact, behave and think. Personality is formed from various experiences that each individual experiences in his life so that because of these experiences each individual has a different personality. The existence of various character differences will be one of the demands on leaders to understand the character of each employee and unite these various character differences to become a team with good performance so that company goals can be achieved. This is in line with research conducted by Kurniawan, et al (2022) and Sya'baniah, et al (2019) which states that personality has a positive effect on employee performance. Apart from religiosity and personality, another factor that drives employee performance is the work environment. According to Basuki & Susilowati (in Wagiyono et al, 2020: 155) the work environment is all elements that have an influence, either directly or indirectly, on individuals or groups in carrying out their activities.

A good work environment includes both physical and non-physical environments that can provide a pleasant, safe and peaceful impression for employees. According to Sedarmayanti (2009) the physical work environment is the environment around employees that is able to influence them

both directly and indirectly in physical form. The physical environment that has a direct influence includes tables, chairs, computers, printing machines and other supporting equipment that can be seen by employees. Meanwhile, the physical environment that does not have a direct influence includes room comfort, calm, air circulation, smells, and so on that cannot be seen but can be felt. Comfortable environmental conditions will increase enthusiasm for active work and employees will be able to concentrate on completing their responsibilities so that employee performance can continue to be optimal. This is supported by research conducted by Prameswara and Priatna (2021) which states that the physical work environment has a significant effect on employee performance. Apart from that, the physical work environment has a significant effect on employee performance in research conducted by Rivalita and Ferdian (2020).

Perhutani is one of the BUMN (State-Owned Enterprises) which is responsible for managing state forest resources for the islands of Java and Madura. Based on data obtained from the Probolinggo City KPH office, the performance of Probolinggo City KPH employees has not shown an overall assessment that is classified as high but there is still employee performance that is classified as medium or low.

Based on the results of observations, it shows that the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees succeeded in realizing the work program at 89.2% of the target to be achieved. This shows that the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees is included in the medium category with employee performance classes divided into 3 classes (Azwar, 2012): Thus, real and directed efforts are still needed for companies consistently and continuously to be able to improve performance Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees are able to achieve maximum targets so that the company's performance can also increase. Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees have the habit of always carrying out dhuhr and asr worship activities in congregation. When the call to prayer started to be played, several employees immediately left their work rooms and headed to the mosque provided by the office. This is of course a very positive phenomenon for maintaining the psychological atmosphere of employees by separating prayer hours which should be on time with working hours. However, not all employees do this. There are still some employees who choose to continue completing their work and postpone worship until their work is finished. So there is a difference in the priority of activities, both of which are obligations.

When carrying out internships, researchers found different attitudes and behavior for each employee's personality. Some employee behavior in each department is different. Employees in the Human Resources (HR) and general departments tend to have a friendly attitude towards other individuals, they often choose to discuss small matters to difficult decisions to make, and are always able to create an atmosphere for communicating with other people. However, in the finance section and IT section, the attitudes and behavior of employees tend to like to be quiet when working

and focus on their respective jobs. Employees in the finance and IT sections also occasionally chat, but not as often as in the HR and general departments. Apart from that, there are several employees who are patient and deft in responding and teaching students as interns when they experience difficulties in doing the work given by KPH Probolinggo employees. However, there are also several KPH Probolinggo employees who are also firm in providing work so that sometimes interns are hesitant to start asking questions first regarding the difficulties they encounter and prefer to wait to be given the opportunity to ask questions by the supervising employee.

The physical work environment in each department is also different. There are still facilities that do not support optimizing the performance of KPH Probolinggo employees in each department, such as hot rooms because the existing air conditioning is not optimal. Apart from that, the color of the walls in several sections of the workroom are also starting to fade and are filled with cobwebs. The work chairs provided and those received by employees also vary. This lack of physical work environment support will of course reduce the optimal performance of employees as when they work they are disturbed by inadequate facilities

II. RESEARCH METHODS

Based on the background and problem formulation that has been prepared, the type of research used in this research is explanatory research. This research uses quantitative research methods with the research object being employees of the Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) with a focus on religiosity, personality and the physical work environment on employee performance. In this research, a predetermined population was used, namely all employees of the Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH), totaling 72 people. The samples used in this research were all 72 Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. Sampling in this study used nonprobability sampling using saturated samples. In this research, the type of data used is quantitative data, where the data used is data from the results of respondents' answers that have been submitted through distributing questionnaires.

III. RESEARCH RESULT

This research was conducted on KPH Probolinggo employees. The results of the validity test show that each indicator obtained a calculated r greater than the r table and a significance value below 0.05, so it can be interpreted that all the statements in the questionnaire used as data collection instruments in the research are valid. The results of the reliability test show that each variable obtained a Cronbach Alpha value of more than 0.60, so it can be interpreted that the instrument used in this research is reliable. The data normality test is carried out to determine whether a data distribution is normal or not. Based on the Asymp value. Sig. (2-tailed) of 0.200 and above a significant value of 0.05 so that the residual data is normally distributed.

Multiple linear regression analysis is a linear relationship between two or more independent variables and the dependent variable. Multiple regression analysis in this research was used to determine the influence of Religiosity (X1), Personality (X2), and Physical Work Environment (X3) on Performance (Y) of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis which shows the N value or the number of samples in this study as many as 72 respondents. Meanwhile, the R Square value shows that Religiosity (X1), Personality (X2), and Physical Work Environment (X3) influence Performance (Y) by 69.9% while the remaining 30.1% is influenced by other factors not used in the research. This. The regression equation is explained

$$Y = 5.234 + 0.109 X1 + 0.180 X2 + 0.197 X3 + e$$

Based on the equation above, we get a constant value of 5.234, which means that if the value of the variables Religiosity (X1), Personality (X2), and Physical Work Environment (X3) is equal to zero then Performance (Y) is a constant, namely 5.234. The coefficient value of the religiosity variable (X1) is a positive value of 0.109, which means that if religiosity increases, the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees will experience an increase. Every one unit increase in the religiosity variable (X1) will increase performance by 0.109 with the assumption that personality (X2) and Physical Work Environment (X3) are constant. The coefficient value of the personality variable (X2) is a positive value of 0.180, which means that the personality tends towards allocentrism. then the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees will increase. Every time the tendency for allocentric traits increases by one unit of personality variable (X2) will increase performance by 0.180 with the assumption that religiosity (X1) and Physical Work Environment (X3) remain constant. The coefficient value of the physical work environment variable (X3) is a positive value of 0.197, which means that if the work environment gets better, the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees will increase. Every one unit increase in the physical work environment variable (X3) will increase performance by 0.197 with the assumption that religiosity (X1) and personality (X2) remain constant.

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out using the t test which aims to determine the influence of the independent variables namely religiosity (X1), personality (X2), physical work environment (X3) partially on the dependent variable namely Performance (Y).

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, it shows that the results of testing the influence of the religiosity variable on performance obtained a calculated t value of 2.704 which is greater than the t table of 1.993. Meanwhile, the significance obtained was 0.009, which was smaller than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. The results of testing the influence of personality variables on performance obtained a calculated t value of 3.402 which is greater than the t table of 1.993. Meanwhile, the significance obtained was 0.001, which was smaller than the predetermined significance

level of 0.05. The results of testing the influence of physical work environment variables on performance obtained a calculated t value of 2.978 which is greater than the t table of 1.993. Meanwhile, the significance obtained was 0.004, which was smaller than the predetermined significance level of 0.05. So it can be stated that H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted, which indicates that religiosity, personality, physical work environment have a partially significant effect on the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *The Effect of Religiosity on Employee Performance*

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the religiosity variable in this study has the results of a partially significant effect on the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. Religiosity has an effect on employee performance which occurs in each individual due to certain reasons. In such cases, the nature of obedience to God is ingrained in each individual without worrying about anything else. Apart from that, the attitude of religiosity has been applied to himself, such as carrying out religious services well outside working hours, good daily practices to increase religious knowledge and even giving alms which he does when not together with other employees. The results of this research are in line with Dr Roxane Gervais, a psychologist from the Health and Safety Laboratory in Stockport, England (In Rif'an, 2022) who stated that the more religious a person is, the smaller the possibility of feeling anxiety, depression and fatigue. A person who has a good level of religious awareness will work well and have good performance too. Therefore, the higher the religiosity, the better the employee's performance.

➤ *The Influence of Personality on Employee Performance*

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the personality variables in this study have a partially significant effect on the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. This research shows that because female employees tend to like to interact with each other during or not during working hours, employees aged 18-25 years tend to always want to be involved with senior employees to get new things that can be learned in the world of work, and employees always try to engage and interact with each other so that group interests always come first compared to personal interests. The results of this research are in line with Schermerhon (in Sya'baniah, 2019) who states that personality is a tendency to respond positively or negatively to someone or something around them. If an employee has a positive attitude towards work, the employee will work harder to give the best to the responsibilities they have been assigned.

➤ *The Influence of the Physical Work Environment on Employee Performance*

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the physical work environment variable in this study has a partially significant effect on the performance of Probolinggo City Forest Management Unit (KPH) employees. The results of this research are in line with Sihombing (2014) who stated

that the physical work environment is one of the elements that must be maximized by companies to improve employee performance. Apart from that, previous research conducted by Prihastoto and Adi (2019) stated that this research was conducted to determine the influence of the physical work environment on the performance of PT Prime Line Internasional Malang employees. The research results show that there is a significant influence of the physical work environment on employee performance. This is also supported by research conducted by Wangi et al (2020) to determine the influence of the physical work environment on employee performance with the object being employees of PT Arwana Citra Mulia Tbk. In this research, the physical work environment had a significant positive effect on the performance of PT Arwana Citra Mulia Tbk employees, which indicates that the better the employees of PT Arwana Citra Mulia Tbk. the better the resulting performance will be.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the analysis carried out in this research, it can be concluded that Religiosity, Personality and Physical Work Environment have a partially significant effect on employees of the Probolinggo City Forest Stakeholder Unit (KPH). This proves that the high level of religiosity and allocentric personality embedded in each employee that is brought into the world of work as well as a good physical work environment will improve the performance of employees of the Probolinggo City Forest Stakeholder Unit (KPH).

REFERENCES

- [1]. Afandi, P. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Cetakan pertama*. Yogyakarta: Nusa Media
- [2]. Akta, M. 2014. *Moderating effect of idiocentrism and allocentrism on person- organization person-job fit and work attitudes relationship. Cross Cultural Management*, 21 (3) : 293-294.
- [3]. Alavi, S. B. 2015. *Measurement of Vertical and Horizontal Idiocentrism and Allocentrism in Small Groups. Small Group Research*, 38 (4) : 557.
- [4]. Alfisyah, K. Dewi. & Anwar, M. Khoirul. 2018. Pengaruh Religiusitas Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Muslim Kantor Pusat PT Perkebunan Nusantara XI. *Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 1 (2):99-107.
- [5]. Ancok, D. & Suroso, F. N. 2011. Psikologi Islami: Solusi Islam atas Problemproblem Psikologi. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- [6]. Azwar, S. 2012. Penyusunan Skala Psikologi Edisi Dua. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
- [7]. Fatmala, K. 2019. Pengaruh Kepribadian dan Motivasi terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Pada Kantor Kementerian Agama Kota Pematangsiar. *Jurnal Manajemen*, 5 (1):66-76.
- [8]. Feist & J. Feist, 2014. Teori Kepribadian. Jakarta: Salemba Humanika.
- [9]. Ghozali, I. 2016. Aplikasi Analisis Multivariete Dengan Program IBM SPSS 23 (Edisi 8). Cetakan ke VIII. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [10]. Ghozali, I. 2017. Model Persamaan Struktural Konsep Dan Aplikasi Program AMOS 24. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- [11]. Ghufron, M. N., & Risnawinta, R. S. 2017. Teori-Teori Psikologi. Yogyakarta: ARR-RUZZ MEDIA.
- [12]. Hariyadi, I., Mahmudi, L. N. 2020. Pengaruh Religiusitas terhadap Kinerja Pegawai (Studi Kasus Pada Suryamart Soekarno-Hatta Ponorogo Tahun 2019). *E- Journal Unida Gontor*, 6 (2):159-174
- [13]. Iliste, A. 2017. The Personality Dimension Of Idiocentrism-Allocentrism Among International Students. Master Thesis. Swedia : Umea University.
- [14]. Indrastuti, S. 2021. Pengaruh Kepribadian terhadap Kinerja Karyawan dengan Variabel Intervening Kompetensi Karyawan Pada Mutiara Merdeka Hotel Pekanbaru. *Jurnal Ekonomi KIAT*, 32 (2) : 98-107.
- [15]. Jannah, N. 2021. Pengaruh Religiusitas, Lingkungan Kerja, dan Shift Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai (Studi SPG Matahari Departemen Store Lippo Plaza Kota Jambi). Skripsi. Jambi : UIN Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin.Sugiyono.2004. Metode Penelitian. Bandung: Alfabeta
- [16]. Lazarusli, B., Lestari, S., Abdullah, G., Sudrajat, R., & Suciptaningsih, O. A. 2014. Penguatan Peran Keluarga Dalam Pembentukan Kepribadian Anak Melalui Seminar dan Pendampingan Masalah Keluarga. *E-Dimas : Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 5 (1):1-12.
- [17]. Mirzani, N. & Dharmawan, D. 2017. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja dan Kompetensi Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT Sinar Mas Land Tbk tangerang. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis Krisnadwipayana*, 5 (3).
- [18]. Moehariono. 2012. "Pengukuran Kinerja Berbasis Kompetensi". Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada.
- [19]. Santoso, S. 2019. Optimalisasi Pendidikan Karakter Melalui Kerjasama Madrasah dan Masyarakat DI Madrasah Aliyah Negeri 1 Indragiri Hiril. Tesis. Jambi
- [20]. : Universitas Islam Negeri Sulthan Thaha Saifuddin Jambi.
- [21]. Shaari, R., Sarip, A., & Ramadhinda, S. 2022. Kajian Pengaruh Kerja Fisik Lingkungan Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Internasional Penelitian Akademik dalam Bisnis dan Ilmu Sosial*, 12 (12): 1734 – 1742.
- [22]. Sidauruk, S. A. 2019. Pengaruh Kepribadian dan Lingkungan Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Departemen Pabrik PT Toba Pulp Lestari, Tbk. Skripsi. Medan : Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- [23]. Sihombing, U. 2014. Pengaruh Keterlibatan Dalam pengambilan Keputusan, Penilaian pada Lingkungan Kerja dan Motivasi Berprestasi Terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Pamong Praja. <http://www.dupdiknas.go.id>.
- [24]. Wangi, N. K. V., Bahiroh, E., & Imron, A. 2020. Dampak Kesehatan Dan Keselamatan Kerja, Beban Kerja, Dan Lingkungan Kerja Fisik Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *JMB : Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis*, 7 (1):40-50.
- [25]. Widiyanti, N., Abdullah, M. L., & Hendrarto, A. 2020. Eksistensi Kepribadian Manusia Melalui Pendekatan Tafsir Al-Qur'an. *Prophetic: Professional, Empathy and Islamic Counseling Journal*, 3 (1):15-24.

- [26]. Wulandari, R. 2017. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Fisik Terhadap Kinerja Pegawai Bidang Sekretariat Pada Dinas Perindustrian Perdagangan, Koperasi, Dan Usaha Mikro Kecil Dan Menengah Provinsi Kalimantan Timur Di Samarinda. *eJournal Administrasi Bisnis*, 5(1):150-154.